

IDENTIFICATION OF KNOWLEDGE LEVEL AIMED TO MANAGEMENT OF EMERGENCY STOCKS IN PUBLIC HEALTH UNITS, THE BASIS OF A TIMELY PREPARATION FOR PANDEMIC PERIODS

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Abstract

Purpose –Development of a practical guide for planning and carrying out the processes of making emergency stocks, for the public health units in Romania, in order to identify and implement good practices within them.

Methodology/approach - The research methods that will be used are the study of the specialized literature, the survey, the case study.

Findings – The importance of this topic can be justified at least by the following arguments: contributes to the development of the state of knowledge in the management of emergency stocks in public health units, having direct implications on their performance management;

Research limitations/implications – the lack of openness of the personnel directly involved, in the official recognition of the difficulties encountered during the pandemic, related to stock management.

Practical implications – Theoretically, through this paper I want to bring more knowledge regarding the definition and analysis of methods for efficient planning of stocks for a pandemic context of health units..

Originality/value – I can say that this work is both valuable and original because the claims are not just theoretical. The main author of this paper is not just a theoretician, but a man who worked in the health system during the pandemic, and his work involves exactly ensuring the supplies needed by the medical staff.

Key words: Stock management, Guide, Good practices.

Introduction

The motivation for choosing this topic was the desire to identify ways to streamline stock planning activities, respectively the supply process of public health units in Romania, which faced a number of shortcomings in securing stocks of protective equipment, disinfectants, basic medical devices and in vitro diagnostic medical devices in the context of the pandemic. These problems were caused by the lack of a legal framework or guidelines, dependence on imports from Asian countries, but also by the lack of effectiveness and efficiency in the supply processes and the establishment of emergency stocks. By designing a system to integrate organizational objectives with the activities and costs of products and services, I want to present the impact of the information obtained on the efficiency of cost management, inventory, resource allocation and / or process efficiency.

The motivation and importance of this work comes precisely from the perspective of the less happy experiences lived practically in the public health units in Romania, in the context of the two years since the beginning of the COVID crisis 19.

Among the priorities of the work from the point of view of stock management, is the definition of a way to develop the necessary protective equipment, disinfectants, basic medical devices and in vitro diagnostic medical devices for a pandemic context of public health units, and the performance of

processes supply in public health units, which is a priority area but also a dynamic one, and whose main objective must be to bring added value.

The subject of the topic is motivated firstly by the fact that an efficient planning of the needs, respectively of the supply process of the public health units in Romania must be placed in the present pandemic and post-pandemic and economic context, and secondly for efficient use of public funds.

The context of the work

At the beginning of the Pandemic, public hospitals in Romania carried out their activities according to the specific legislation from that date. This did not require the existence of personal protective equipment (PPE), disinfectants and basic medical devices in emergency stocks. Moreover, the onset of the Pandemic in Romania, which took place at the end of February 2020, the beginning of March 2020, when the public hospitals in Romania had not concluded financing contracts with the Health Insurance Companies, and according to the legislation, the funds used were at the level of 1/12 of the contract concluded last year, but with some prudence in committing expenses. Thus, even from the point of view of financing, at that time, the public sanitary units did not have the possibility of creating emergency stocks. In a public hospital and not only, before the onset of the Pandemic as protective medical materials and devices, protective gloves (sterile examination and surgical), disposable caps, impermeable visitor gowns, impermeable sterile gowns (mainly in OR), disposable surgical masks. The need for medical protective materials and devices, disinfectants and in vitro diagnostic medical devices (SARS COV2 tests), has increased significantly both in quantity and in the range of products. Moreover, the Asian market being almost closed, these materials, as well as the medical devices used in the treatment of patients, were completely absent. A supply bubble has been created, but also a speculative bubble. All this, as well as the little information about the SARS Cov 2 virus, created a panic among medical professionals and auxiliary medical personnel.

The objectives of the paper

To this end, this paper has the following specific objectives:

1. Carrying out an analysis of the existence of the necessary emergency stocks in a pandemic context and recommendations for the improvement of good practices in their realization;
2. Identifying and implementing best practices for planning for emergency stockpiles in a pandemic context;
3. Development of a practical guide for planning and carrying out the processes of making emergency stocks, for the public health units in Romania, in order to identify and implement good practices within them.

General aspects and theoretical foundations regarding the establishment of emergency stocks

According to Law No. 95/2006 Republished on health reform, the manager of a health unit is the one who makes the resources of an organization turn into results. And one of the most important roles of a manager is to make decisions. The use of a practical guide for making emergency stocks, for public health units in Romania, can be used in the decision-making process.

The manager must be effective and efficient. It has to do exactly what it has to do, namely to use resources as economically as possible. According to the specialty literature, effectiveness is more important than efficiency.

According to the provisions of Law 98/2016, the Annual Public Procurement Program must take into account the objective needs and their degree of prioritization. Within the public health units, according to Order no. 921/2006 for establishing the duties of the management committee within the public hospital, the management committee elaborates, analyzes and proposes for approval to the manager the development plan of the hospital during the term of office, based on the written proposals of the medical board, the project of the hospital's income and expenditure budget, in compliance with the population's medical service needs, the development of medical technologies, guidelines and medical practice protocols.

A major importance in the correct conduct of public procurement during a budget year is the planning of the procurement process. If this planning process is not carried out properly, it can generate deviations from the legislation, errors and problems in the stage of the award procedure and in the implementation of the contract.

At the same time, public procurement, at the level of contracting authorities, is also associated with the acceptance of a managerial function in the context of Law no. 98/2016, since:

"The notion of acquisition should be interpreted, in a broad sense, as obtaining benefits from the works, products, services in question, without necessarily implying a transfer of ownership to the contracting authorities" (paragraph 4 of the Preamble of Directive 2014/25);

Public procurement plays a key role in the strategy "Europe 2020, A European strategy for smart, green and inclusive growth [...]", representing one of the tools to be used to achieve smart, sustainable and inclusive growth, while ensuring while the most efficient use of public funds." (paragraph 1 of the Preamble of Directive 2014/25).

Public procurement is used at contracting authority level for the application of national policies in certain areas, in order to achieve objectives established through national/regional/local strategies.

Planning the procurement process is crucial. Failure to do so causes errors and problems in the awarding procedure stage and in the implementation of the contract.

The methodology of implementing a practical guide for making emergency stocks, the integration of the information provided by a practical guide for planning and running the procedures for making emergency stocks, in the planning, budgeting and forecasting processes, quantifying the impact generated by the application of a guide, it can represent one of the tools that must be used to achieve intelligent, sustainable and favorable growth, ensuring the most efficient use of public funds.

The methodology of applying a guide to making emergency stocks

The general purpose of the practical guide for planning and carrying out procedures for the realization of emergency stocks is to establish the way of carrying out the activity, the departments and the persons involved, to give assurances regarding the existence of the appropriate documentation for the performance of the activity, to ensure continuity the activity, including in conditions of personnel fluctuation, to support the audit and/or other competent bodies in audit and/or control actions, and the credit orderer, in making the decision.

The specific purpose of the guide is to establish the necessary documentation and stages for the preparation under legal conditions and in compliance with the legal deadlines for the realization of emergency stocks.

If we were to define this Guide, we can say that it describes the activities that must be carried out within public health units, related to the elaboration in conditions of legality, regularity and in compliance with the legal deadlines for planning and carrying out the establishment of emergency stocks.

In its contents, it is necessary to find the list of the main activities that depend on and/or that depend on the activity of planning and carrying out the establishment of emergency stocks, the departments providing data of the activity, the departments benefiting from the results of the activity, the departments involved in the activity process, legal regulations, responsibilities, required resources, process diagram and deliverables.

It is of major importance to establish a Commission at the level of the health unit made up of professionals from the following fields: doctors and epidemiologists, laboratory assistants, infectious disease specialists, ATI, economists from the finance, supply and procurement departments, as well as lawyers. The role of this committee is to establish the Nomenclature of emergency stocks and the quantities required for a period of at least 60 days, depending on the capacity of the unit and its specifics. So that, at the initiation of the process of planning and carrying out public procurement procedures and the supply process, the head of the internal department specialized in procurement, who submits an administrative document in the first month of the last quarter of the year for the following year, requesting the start of the procurement process elaboration of the Annual Public Procurement Strategy, this Nomenclature can be submitted.

The substantiation of the Product Nomenclature within the guide for making emergency stocks

As we have shown previously, the need for protective medical materials and devices, disinfectants and in vitro diagnostic medical devices (SARS COV2 tests), has increased significantly both in quantity and in the range of products. Stocks in public health facilities could not cover the need. Thus, the central public authorities requested from them a series of daily and weekly information/reports, in the form of the attached tables.

Tables 1, 2 and 3 represent the situation on the first date reported by a regional hospital, to each authority. The most representative data are those presented in table 4, where we can see the low percentage of coverage of the estimated needs for a period of 45 days, on March 30, 2020. Thus, for the category Individual medium protective equipment for staff (gowns) the need was covered in a percentage of 14%, for the category surgical masks - 10%, FFP masks - 2%, surgical and examination gloves - 60%, coveralls - 7%, underwear - 0%, hand sanitizer by rubbing - 8%, Hand sanitizer by washing - 41%, chlorine disinfectant - 10%. To highlight these percentages even more, if we look at the existing quantity of surgical masks in stock, namely 20750 pieces, and relate it to the number of employees at that date of approximately 4300, but also to the indications of the number of hours of use of surgical masks between 4-8 hours, we can conclude that the situation did not look good at all. In the next 30-60 days, the situation of the supplied quantities did not undergo major changes, and the existing stocks were running out. Therefore, for a good management of stocks, it was decided to make users responsible, by introducing registers to record the use of three types of protective equipment, highlighted in table 4.

Prior to the onset of the pandemic, the average monthly consumption of surgical masks in the mentioned hospital was 20,000 pieces per month, sterile gowns 5,000 pieces per month, examination gloves 400,000 pieces per month. The supply of these products is normally made in the last week of the month for the following month. For overalls and FFP2 masks, for example, before the onset of the pandemic, there was no need for these products. If we compare the average monthly consumptions in the pre-pandemic period, with those needed since the beginning of the pandemic, we easily notice that the need has increased at least 6 times.

On 29.03.2020, the Ministry of Health issued Order 533, published in MO PI 263/2020-03-31, regarding the approval of the Plan of measures for the preparation of hospitals in the context of the COVID-19 coronavirus epidemic and the List of support hospitals for patients test positive for the SARS-CoV-2 virus. In its content, there were also Regulations regarding personal protective equipment (PPE):

"1. The recommendations "Rational use of PPE in the context of COVID-19", a document developed by the National Center for Surveillance and Control of Communicable Diseases within the National Institute of Public Health together with the Association for the Prevention and Control of Nosocomial Infections, according to the recommendations of the World Organization, are considered minimum criteria of Health in the field (Interim Guidance February 27, 2020). 2. A documented training, as well as a practical one, will be carried out with all personnel for the appropriate use of personal protective equipment. (...) VI. It will be ensured that the icons on the website of the National Institute of Public Health (www.insp.gov.ro) related to the infection of COVID-19, posted under the heading " Information for medical personnel". Rational use of personal protective equipment in the context of the COVID-19 infection. ARE YOU COMING. Preventive measures in the context of COVID-19 Based on the available evidence, the SARS-CoV-2 virus is transmitted from person to person by direct contact and by Flügge droplets. People at greatest risk of infection are those who are in direct contact with a patient with COVID-19 or who care for patients with COVID-19. Prevention and limitation measures are essential both in the field of medical assistance and at the community level. The most effective preventive measures for the community include: - frequent hand hygiene with a hydro-alcoholic rubbing solution if the hands are not visibly dirty or with water and soap if the hands are dirty; (...)Medical personnel must apply additional precautions to protect themselves and prevent transmission during medical care. Precautions to be taken by medical personnel caring for patients with COVID-19 include using PPE appropriately; this involves both the selection of appropriate personal protective equipment and its appropriate fitting and unequipment. Recommendations for optimal use of available personal protective equipment.

Table 1

County	Unitate sanitară	Products													
		Surgical masks		FFP2 masks		FFP3 masks		Protective overalls		Biocides TP1 (personal) I		Biocides TP 2 (surfaces) I			
		a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b		
		20,300.00	20,300.00	-	-	189.00	189.00	189.00	189.00	2,085.00	2,085.00	2,085.00	2,085.00	5,177.50	

a) existing in stock on 21.03.2020
b) of which purchased by exception from GEO no. 11/2020

Table 2

No	Product	Initial stock	ordered	Reception	Distributed	Final stock
1	Surgical mask	20,000.00	105,000.00		-	20,000.00
2	FFP2 mask	-	-		-	-
3	FFP3 mask	168.00	-		-	168.00
4	Surgical gloves	17,730.00	26,000.00		-	17,730.00
5	Protective overalls	663.00	500.00		-	663.00
6	Biocides TP1 (personal)	1,771.00	240.00		-	1,771.00
7	Biocides TP 2 (surfaces)	6,315.50	5,637.00		-	6,315.50

24.03.2020

Table 3

Situation on 30.03.2020				
Product name	UM	45 days re-quired	Stock	% coverage required
Protective overalls	pcs	10,000	692.00	7%
Sort UF	pcs	10,000	-	0%
UF underwear	pcs	27,000	-	0%
Individual medium protection equipment for staff (STERILE GOWNS)	pcs	82,000	11,232.00	14%
Individual medium protection equipment for staff (visitor GOWNS)	pcs			
Individual medium protection equipment for staff (non-sterile impermeable GOWNS)	pcs			
Short gloves (pcs) (surgical + examination)	pcs	1,340,000.00	799,622.00	60%
Surgical gloves	pairs	20,000.0	32,422.00	162%
Examination gloves	pcs	1,320,000	767,200.00	58%
Protective glasses	pcs	4,500	492.00	11%
Protective visor	pcs	10,000	-	0%
FFP2 medical masks	pcs	10,000	200.00	2%
FFP3 medical masks	pcs	10,000	242.00	2%
Surgical mask	pcs	200,000	20,750.00	10%
Rubber boots	pcs	1,000	-	0%
Disinfectant TP1 for the hygienic disinfection of hands by rubbing	l	2,000	164.00	8%
Disinfectant TP1 for the hygienic disinfection of hands by washing	l	4,430	1,797.00	41%
Disinfectant TP2 for high level disinfection for critical surfaces	l	2,000	687.00	34%
Disinfectant TP2 ultra-fast, ready-made for critical medical surfaces and devices	l	4,000	858.00	21%
Disinfectant for semi-critical surfaces	l	4,000	1,797.00	45%
Disinfectant for non-critical surfaces	l	1,000	-	0%
Aeromicroflora disinfectant set	l	2,500	795.00	32%
instruments	l	1,960	2,251.00	115%
Chlorigen	pcs	192,000	18,600.00	10%

Table 4

Clinic/compartment/laboratory							
SHEET REGARDING THE RECEIPT AND USE OF THE PROTECTIVE PRODUCT - SURGICAL MASK							
No	Name and surname of the user	Date	Hour	Salon / location of use or no. of FOB	pcs	Work	Signature
1							
2							
3							
4							
5							

Given the global shortage of personal protective equipment, the following strategies can facilitate the optimal use of PPE (Fig. 1). Ensuring that personal protective equipment (PPE) is used rationally and correctly Personal protective equipment should be used based on the risk of exposure (e.g. type of activity) and transmission dynamics of the pathogen (e.g. contact, droplets or aerosols). Excessive use of PPE will further impact supply difficulties. By considering the following recommendations, the rational use of PPE can be ensured: – The type of PPE used when providing care to patients with COVID-19 will vary depending on the situation, the health personnel and the activity performed (table 1). – Medical personnel involved in the direct care of patients must use the following PPE: gowns, gloves, mask and eye protection (goggles or face shield). – Specifically, for aerosol-generating procedures for patients with COVID-19 (eg, intubation, non-invasive ventilation, tracheostomy, cardiopulmonary resuscitation, manual ventilation before intubation, bronchoscopy, gastroscopy, and collection of PCR COVID tests) medical personnel must to use protection, gloves, gowns, FFP2 and FFP3 masks; waterproof aprons will also be used, if the coveralls/gowns are not waterproof.”

Fig. 1. Strategies for optimizing the availability of personal protective equipment (PPE)¹

Thus using the information from the requested reports as well as from Order 533/2020, depending on the specifics of the health units, the Nomenclature of the emergency stocks of each unit should contain at least the existing products in tables 1, 2, and 3.

Conclusions

Through this work, a part of the reality experienced in public health units was made known, and under this aspect, it was desired to generate recommendations for improving good practices. The objective of making necessary emergency stocks in a pandemic context and implementing good practices - unitary procedures, in the public sanitary units in Romania, is a necessary and real one, in order to improve the efficiency and performance of the procurement, supply processes, as well as and efficient use of public funds. The less pleasant experiences, it is necessary to use them to build a better future. Therefore, we can use as reference products in the creation of emergency stocks, the products used during this period of the pandemic, mentioned in all reports, with minimum compliance with the indications for use in Order 533/2022.

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PUBLIC PROCUREMENT GUIDE administered by ANAP
Directive 2014/25
Law no. 98/2016 on public procurement, with subsequent amendments and additions
Order no. 921/2006 for establishing the duties of the management committee within the public hospital
Law No. 95/2006 Republished on health reform

¹ Figure 1 is reproduced in facsimile.